

Qualitative Method: Essential Tool for Human Geography Research

Tania Yeasmin¹, Md Shafiqul Islam^{1,2}

¹GIS & Environmental Specialist, GIS & RS Solution Email: yeasmintania03@gmail.com

²Consultant, EQMS Consulting Limited, Dhaka, Bangladesh Email: islamshafiquldm@gmail.com

Background

Qualitative method is an essential tool and significantly used in several areas of human geography research (Winchester, H., & Rofo, M. 2010). It helps elucidate the complex relationship of human beings and their surrounding environment by providing valuable insights into sociocultural and spatial interactions. The strength of qualitative research is to explain the human side of any situation through a textual explanation. People's perception, observation, interaction and behavior take precedence over secondary data sources in this method and gives full emphasis on human dimension. Several qualitative methods are used in human geography research. This article will specifically highlight Focus Group Discussion (FGD), Key Informant Interview (KII) and the Photovoice method. It will also explore the ability and effectiveness of those methods to understand the intricate human and environmental interactions.

Focus Group Discussions (FGD)

Focus Group Discussion (FGD) is an essential qualitative research method and data collection technique widely used in human geography research. This discussion incorporates small groups of people to solicit their thoughts, ideas and perceptions of a specific topic that is usually facilitated by a moderator. FGD incorporates participants who are directly connected with the topic of discussion with some guided questions that they can freely discuss. Usually, each focus group ranges from 3 to 21 participants with a median of 10 (O. Nyumba et al., 2018). This discussion aimed to identify common viewpoints as well as the points of disagreement within the targeted community which would certainly be impossible to achieve through individual interviews or surveys.

An example can be taken from a re-envisioned energy system project, where the participant of an FGD can be the local community and energy stockholders. Discussion with the targeted participants will reflect their thoughts on shifting from fossil fuel to renewable energy, address social inequality and initiatives to mitigate climate change impacts. The study aims to identify people's perception on energy storage transformation and the impacts on society and environment. Participants can share the challenges of adapting renewable energy as a solution to power crisis, their willingness to shift from traditional energy sources to sustainable options and suggestions for effective implementation of this solution at local level. Participants' perspective will help to develop initiative which reflects community value, to identify factors that community prioritize and to better understand the barriers for project implementation.

Key Informant Interview (KII)

Key Informant Interview (KII) is an important qualitative method involving one-to-one, in-depth interviews with an individual known as 'Key Informant' with specialized knowledge about a topic of interest. This method is crucial for analyzing complex scenarios where particular knowledge is needed. Data collected from KII are paramount as they offer a granular understanding of a certain topic from an expert's perspective rather than analyzing different aspects of the experiences.

When assessing the environmental and social impact of a solar power park project, KII can be facilitated with project developers and engineers, community leaders, government representatives (officials from department of environment, agriculture, forestry, livestock, parks and wildlife, planning and housing, fire and rescue and social welfare), environmental experts, energy sector professionals and financial stockholders. The Environmental and social impacts of this project can be both positive and negative. The KIIs will help to identify potential negative environmental impacts, including effects on soil, air and water quality, ecology, land use and local wildlife. Possible mitigations measures of identified impacts can also be suggested by the subject matter specialist. Positive environmental impacts comprise reducing greenhouse gas emissions, less dependency on fossil fuels, ecosystem conservation and less waste generation. Additionally, negative social impacts of this project may be displacement by land acquisition, occupational and community health safety concerns, local conflict, social inequity due to uneven distribution of the project benefits, alteration of local land use pattern and impact on cultural and historical heritage. Positive impacts include increasing community awareness of renewable energy use, local employment opportunities, improved energy access, socio-economic development and social equity. KII can be instrumental in understanding a solar power park project's comprehensive social and environmental impacts and can promote environmental sustainability and social wellbeing.

Photovoice Method

Photovoice is an emerging qualitative method that enable participants to document, interpret and communicate their experiences and views through photography and storytelling (Wang, C., & Burris, M. A., 1997). This action-based participatory method is considered a valuable tool for examining place-based experiences and local knowledge. It allows the participants to directly involve in the research process by empowering them to document their-real life problems within the community. Photographs and their narratives serve as a bridge between researchers and participants. This approach also breaks the conventional boundary between researcher and participant, making the research more inclusive and democratic.

For instance, in a study on environmental justice for indigenous community, participants from the community are asked to take photos of local environmental issues, such as environmental pollution, deforestation, waste generation and other environmental matters. These images, accompanied by the story behind their capture, can provide insights into the visual source of the problem, the associated environmental risks and their effect on community's quality of life. Community can also document the effect on health, social well-being, environment and vulnerable groups (women, children, elderly and low-income households). Photovoice method allows the people of marginalized indigenous community to raise their voice about environmental injustice and drown the concerns of policymakers and the

broader public. Policymakers and environmental organizations can derive inclusive understanding from the evidence and narratives, which can be reflected in more appropriate policies and strategies, highlighting the specific needs and rights of indigenous communities. In this method, community people not only act as beneficiaries but also as active agents addressing the problem and solution on their own.

Conclusion

To conclude, qualitative methods such as FGD, KII and photovoice are indispensable in human geography research and offer a comprehensive understanding of the human and environmental dynamics that shape human experiences. The integration of these techniques helps researchers to triangulate data, validate findings and address research questions from different perspectives. Unlike other methods, qualitative methods can provide nuanced understanding about critical geographic issues such as climate change, environmental justice, disaster management, urbanization, socio-spatial inequality and resource management. By incorporating public perceptions and their experiences, qualitative research in human geography enables us to reform policies and practices to promote an equitable and sustainable society.

References

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